

THE LANGUAGE PHENOMENON OF 'CLEAN'¹

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Abstract: *The paper is an extended work of a previous research presented at a conference. It gives additional information about 'clean' as an adjective. Some significant points are mentioned again but only for the reason of upgrading. The idiomatic usage of 'clean' and the variety of binomials it occurs in are the main issues considered here.*

Keywords: *adjective, clean, idiom, binomial.*

I. Introduction

The intention to study the adjective 'clean' is not motivated for the sake of any special values of the word itself since it cannot be promoted as more prominent than all the rest existing in the language. Although a common one, it could not be claimed to be the most frequent either since the paper has not taken steps to prove it. The source to examine the word is the British National Corpus [6] where the total number of examples with 'clean' are found to be 6180. In more than a half of them 'clean' is used as an adjective. Such prevalence gives reasons to neglect the rest of the usages at least to a certain point and draw the attention to the adjectival usage.

<i>clean (adj)</i>		spoken	written
followed by			
proper n		3	104
common n	animate n	34	208
	inanimate n	227	2377

Table 1. Number of occurrences in BNC concerning 'clean' as an adjective.

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There, the thing easily noticed is the reference to common nouns rather than to proper ones (see Table 1.) and the fact that inanimate occurrences outnumber animate ones. Quite similar is the proportion of written to spoken language occurrences. Such preponderance might be due to arbitrariness of the corpus itself. This fact is by no means crucial, but it is a curious circumstance that might affect consideration which concerns formality and informality in language. On the other hand, as Malkiel puts it “In certain styles, both conversational and literary, the pairing off or massive accumulation of synonyms may become a pervasive feature...” [4]. Also, Sauer and Schwan [6] note that English binomials are important stylistic phenomenon.

No special reasons urge to examine ‘clean’ in binomial structures but the personal conviction that all binomials deserve to be carefully considered. Again it is done with the help of BNC. The data it supplies give also information about the idiomatic aspect which it should not be omitted to dwell on.

II. Idiomatic usage

The idioms that occur in BNC cover almost all the variants given in an online dictionary [8]. Below are some examples of the different idioms occurring in BNC.

Clean as a whistle – 8 occurrences

2791	BMM	W_biography	A	B	C	.told him.' I've never taken anything. I'm as clean as a whistle ; they can test me any time, anywhere.' He
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Clean break – 77 occurrences

2922	CBG	W_newsp_o ther_sports	A	B	C	deal with Puma worth an estimated 500,000, said:' I'll make a clean break from athletics in two years time and I won't be competing anymore.
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Clean slate – 18 occurrences

1389	BLW	W_religion	A	B	C	When things go wrong # Many people today believe that children begin life with a clean slate. Parents are largely responsible for providing the right environment so that their children
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Clean sweep – 53 occurrences

3001	K4T	W_newsp_ot her_sports	A	B	C	swimmers competing with five others from Stockton. Robin Francis (York) made a clean sweep of his four races to win the award for the top ten-year-old boy at
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Come clean – 80 occurrences

1479	CCE	W_religion	A	B	C	helpless and impotent in the Enemy's territory. # SECULARISATION # I must come clean and admit that the concept of secularisation has become extremely confusing in sociological usage.
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Make a clean breast – 2 occurrences

4725	JYF	W_fict_prose	A	B	C	aware that, no matter how conscience and love might insist that she make a clean breast of everything, to confess was something she simply could not do. He
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Squeaky clean – 23 occurrences

4467	HH0	W_fict_prose	A	B	C	button my jacket. The beginning of the main strip in Shelbyville is a squeaky clean residential area. Lawns edge up to the roadside, porches glow in the night
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An interesting thing to mention are the examples with 'clean sheet' where 57% of the occurrences are idiomatic as compared to the smaller number of its literal usage.

III. Binomial usage

A lot in common can be found between idioms and binomials as according to Mc Carty [5] they both are a "type of multi-word unit..." which displays "fixed membership" and "... should be treated as single vocabulary item".

If A_1 is the first conjunct in a binomial and A_2 is the second, then the structure currently examined will be A_1 and A_2 . Using this designation, the following types can be listed:

1) clean and A_2

According to Caballero Rodrigues "Typical binomials involve words that are synonymous or antonymous..." [1]. The majority of cases from BNC come into this group where a variety of synonyms, antonyms, even adjectives with no clear link to 'clean' at first glance stand for the second conjunct. A protruding example among the antonyms is the occurrence of negation by means of adding a negative prefix as in the example below:

1370	ACL	W_religion	A	B	C	of purity that distinguished between clean and unclean animals, clean and unclean foods, clean and unclean people (Jew and gentile) and clean and unclean physical states (
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What Malkiel [4] notes, and namely that “...Modern English displays a very marked partiality to short plus long: either monosyllable plus (normally paroxytonic) disyllable, or two monosyllables of unequal size; rarely a mono- or di-syllable plus a polysyllable” is perfectly applicable to a subgroup where free as the second conjunct is quite prolific (see Table 2).

Binomial	Number of occurrences
clean and free	2
clean and dust free	1
clean and emission-free	1
clean and grease free	4
clean and rust-free	1
clean and free of extraneous matter	1
clean and free of dandruff	1
clean and free of make-up	1
clean and free from dust	1
clean and free from wax or grease	1
clean and free from intruders	1
clean and free from blood	1
clean and free from effluvia	1
clean and free from any loose material	1
clean and virus-free	1

Table 2. Examples from BNC with ‘free’ as the second conjunct

Another subgroup reveals ‘well’ as productive for the second conjunct where all the examples follow the rule of monosyllabic plus *and* plus a much more longer adjective respectively (see Table 3).

Binomial	Number of occurrences
clean and well built	1
clean and well furnished	1
clean and well-manicured	1
clean and well-oiled	1
clean and well organized	1
clean and well run	1
clean and well written	2
clean and well cared-for	2
clean and well-oxygenated	2
clean and well polished	1

Table3. Examples from BNC with ‘well’ as the second conjunct

2) A_1 and clean

Some examples in Table 4 confirm the rule of shorter preceding the longer but others are in a way an odd juxtaposition.

Binomials	Number of occurrences
□enteell and clean	1
cheap and clean	2
comic and clean	1
continent and clean	1
dynamic and clean	1
early and clean	1
economical and clean	1
fast and clean	2
flexible and clean	1
fragrant and clean	1
good and clean	2
hard and clean	2
lovely and clean	2
light and clean	1
not only light and clean	1
naked and clean	1
quick and clean	4
quiet and clean	2
readable and clean	1
□enteelly shabby and not very clean	1
strong and clean	3
slabby and clean	1
swift and clean	1
tiny and not terribly clean	1
uncontaminated and clean	1
uncrowded and clean	1
well kept and clean	1
young and clean	1

Table4. Examples of the second type (from BNC)

Much more are the cases with short adjectives. This is in conformity with the observation of Sauer and Schwan that “Binomials consisting of simple (monomorphemic) words seem to be the largest group...” [6].

Although admitting that it is not the major and the only reason possible for a particular binomial order, Jespersen [3] insists on the significant role of the rhythm. When they rhyme and conjuncts consist of equal number of syllables, it makes the

binomial easier to remember (e.g. *cheap and clean; fast and clean; hard and clean, etc.*).

3) Reversible

In this group Ivanova [2] notices two subgroups which correspond to the correlation between the two occurrences, i.e. if the number of occurrences rises, the possibility for reversibility also rises, and if the number of occurrences is low, then the reversibility is also low. A third subgroup is also possible to differentiate – the one with both structures equally used, e.g. *clean and clear (2)* and *clear and clean (2)*.

If we rely on etymology, we can put *clean* and *smooth*, for example, in the group of synonyms. Therefore, it is not surprising to find out that both orders are possible and the number of their occurrences is relatively close (*clean* and *smooth* - 4 occurrences compared to *smooth and clean* - 2 occurrences).

Conclusion:

The BNC occurrences present 130 types of binomials where 'clean' is in the first place of the conjunct. This is 74% of all the types which leads to the conclusion about strong preference of 'clean' as a first member. Much less, scarcely reaching the number of 29, are the types of binomials where 'clean' is in the second place of the binomial pair. This is 16% of all the types which means that the second place for 'clean' in the binomials is possible, present in users' speech but far from being preferred. And only 18 types occur both ways. This gives 10% of all the binomial types with 'clean' which though arbitrarily an insignificant part gives the idea about flexibility in language.

To acquaint students with the behavior of 'clean' depicted above would result production of more nativelike structures while using English. Also, drawing the attention of the learners to the rhythm of pairs as in the suggested subgroups would facilitate language learning.

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